

Relationship of corporate social responsibility with job attitude and behavior: Employee's perception

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Abstract

Over the past ten years, corporate social responsibility, or CSR, has expanded quickly. Trend is showing that there is a significant increase of society's overall concern about sustainable development with the aid of corporate social responsibility. However, very little attention had ever been paid to the impact of CSR strategies on employees and their particular work attitudes. This study primarily involved a survey, comprised of a questionnaire concerning the perception of CSR, job satisfaction and work behavior. Questionnaire was used to collect data from employees of job workers. The results of this research indicate that CSR contributes to increase job satisfaction and behavior of employees. Employee-level CSR research is still in its early stages. This study examines the influence of workers' perceptions of corporate social responsibility (CSR) on subsequent work attitudes and behaviors in order to better understand its effect on the workforce. A literature-based conceptual framework is put forward. There was a survey done for this study. To investigate the impact of CSR, managers and employees provided data. The results of this study show that workers' work attitudes and behaviors are significantly impacted by CSR. These studies add to the framework for understanding how CSR affects workers' attitudes and behaviours at work.

Keywords: Corporate Social Responsibility, Job Satisfaction, work Behaviors.

Introduction

The "relationship of corporate social responsibility with job attitude and behaviors: Employee perception" is a topic covered by a plethora of ideas. However, these theories differ from variables and methodologies. Numerous studies have discovered that when an organization fulfils its social obligation, it leaves a positive impact on society. Researchers have recently begun to look into how CSR affects workers' attitudes and behaviours at work. Few research, meanwhile, have looked at how CSR affects workers' attitudes and behaviours at work. While various organizations have varied interpretations of what constitutes corporate social responsibility, CSR programs use common tactics. Corporate social responsibility might be very important when it comes to hiring. The concept of corporate social responsibility was first evaluated in the 1950s, and it was further defined in the 1960s, 1970s, and more recently. The terms "corporate conscience," "corporate citizenship," "social performance," and "sustainable responsible business" are other terms for

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corporate social responsibility (CSR). Corporate social responsibility has shaped the corporate environment and demonstrated its effects on companies. CSR is a procedure that demonstrates accountability for the acts of the company and promotes beneficial effects via its operations on the environment, customers, workers, communities, stakeholders, and any other members of the public who could also be regarded as stakeholders.

According to Mallenbaker, "CSR is about how organization manages the business processes to produce an overall positive impact on society". This term only addresses a small portion of society. Carroll (1979, 2008) described business's social responsibility as including its obligations to society in the areas of economics, law, ethics, and philanthropy. The study by MC Wailliams and Siegael (2000), which was published in the "strategy Management Journal," demonstrates the connection between financial and social success. CSR, according to McWilliams and Siegel (2001), is defined as activities taken outside of the company's best interests and legal requirements in order to promote a social good. It's important to remember that CSR entails more than only abiding by the law (McWilliams & Siegel, 2001).

Mallen Baker is the publisher of the World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD) (2004) Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is the endeavour of businesses to act morally, promote economic growth, and enhance the standard of living for employees and their families, as well as the local community and society at large. According to Naukrihub (2009), CSR has two meanings. On the one hand, it demonstrates the moral conduct that a company demonstrates to its internal and external stakeholders (workers and consumers). Conversely, it signifies an organization's obligation to the community and surroundings in which it functions.

In developing nations, the term "corporate social responsibility" (CSR) may be somewhat confusing for small and medium-sized businesses. The CSR Association of Pakistan encourages businesses in Pakistan to adopt CSR practices and principles since they boost an organization's capacity for innovation, productivity, and competitiveness. By fostering increased operational efficiency, better risk management, positive relationships with the investment community, easier access to capital, improved employee relations, deeper ties with communities, and enhanced reputation and branding, corporate social responsibility (CSR) helps make businesses more competitive. The idea of corporate social responsibility is becoming more and more popular in Pakistan and throughout the world. Although the term "corporate social responsibility" (CSR) is not widely used, many consider it to be the private sector's means of incorporating the environmental, social, and economic requirements of their operations. The triple bottom line and the business goal of sustainable development are similar to corporate social responsibility. Apart from being integrated into company structures and procedures, corporate social responsibility (CSR) often entails coming up with creative and proactive answers to societal and environmental problems and working with internal and external stakeholders to enhance CSR performance.

Workplace attitudes and behaviors are another aspect. The phrase "job" refers to a person's present role, their line of work or profession, and their employer as its legal representative. An attitude is a psychological propensity that manifests itself as a degree of favoritism or disfavor towards a certain thing. A person's opinions about their work that make up their connection, beliefs, and sentiments towards it are collectively referred to as their workplace attitude. Workplace attitudes can be conceptualized in two ways. either as an overall or universal subjective sense about a job, or as affective job satisfaction.

Global job attitudes are perceptions of a job that are shaped by the workplace, social context, organizational structure, emotional style, and overall job attributes. employment Involvement,

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Organizational Commitment, Perceived Organizational Support (POS), and Employee Engagement are some examples of distinct employment attributes. An overall emotional state regarding a job, either overall or generally, is referred to as affective work satisfaction.

Now the attitude and behaviors can directly affect the atmosphere and productivity within an organization. Every employee has an attitude towards the environment either good or bad. This attitude can also influence how he performs. Because attitude is an inward feeling, an employee's bad attitude might remain hidden but indirectly affects the organization performance. This study examine the how employee perceptions of CSR impact employee turnover, increase the job satisfaction and organizational behavior.

What's Relationship of Corporate Social Responsibility with Job Attitude and Behavior according the employee perceptive

I.To examine the relationship between corporate social responsibility and employee job attitude.

II.To find out the Employee perception of corporate social responsibility relationship with behavior.

Literature Review

Corporate social responsibility (CSR) has been a significant topic of discussion since its inception approximately fifty years ago. The evolution of CSR encompasses a rich tapestry of history, theories, concepts, models, and themes. This concept has developed a profound and comprehensive understanding within the literature of CSR.

CSR's journey began in the early 20th century, with Bowen's seminal work laying the groundwork. Recognized as the "Father of Social Responsibility" by Carroll in 1999, Bowen's detailed discussions in the first half of the twentieth century were pivotal. His book, "Social Responsibilities of the Businessman" (1953), initially framed CSR as the duty of businessmen to adopt policies and actions aligning with societal objectives and values.

The 1960s saw further evolution of CSR definitions. Keith Davis, a notable figure of the time, introduced CSR in his writings as decisions reflecting an organization's long-term objectives and social responsibility, beyond mere technical interests. He also connected business ethics with CSR, emphasizing the ethical dimensions of social responsibility.

Joseph W. McGuire, another influential voice, offered a more precise definition in his 1963 book, "Business and Society." He argued that corporations have responsibilities beyond economic and legal obligations, encompassing broader societal welfare including politics, community well-being, education, employee happiness, and overall social engagement.

In 1971, the U.S. Committee for Economic Development (CED) further expanded on CSR, emphasizing its role not just in economic growth but in societal development. The CED redefined the business-society relationship, positioning CSR as integral to both economic and social progress.

Overall, CSR's history reflects an evolution from basic business ethics to a comprehensive framework encompassing various societal aspects. It signifies a shift in business perspectives, highlighting the importance of ethical and societal responsibilities alongside economic objectives. In the 1970s, S. Prakash Sethi emerged as a pivotal figure in the discourse on corporate social

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responsibility (CSR). His seminal 1975 article delineated the dimensions of corporate social performance, differentiating between social obligation, social responsibility, and social responsiveness. Sethi described social obligation as corporate behavior driven by market forces or legal constraints, primarily concerned with economic and legal criteria. He expanded the concept of social responsibility to include actions that align with prevailing social norms, values, and performance expectations, transcending mere social obligation.

In 1979, Carroll introduced a model comprising four components of CSR: economic, legal, ethical, and discretionary aspects. This was further developed in 1982 by Dalton and Cosier, who presented a matrix model categorizing actions as 'illegal' or 'legal' and 'irresponsible' or 'responsible.'

The evolution of CSR thought continued into the 1990s. In 1991, Donna J. integrated Carroll's 1979 four-component model and the Wartick and Cochran (1985) model, leading to a three-dimensional CSR framework. This framework consisted of principles, processes, and policies, as outlined in Wartick and Cochran's formulation. Wood, in the same year, reinterpreted these dimensions, outlining three principles of CSR. She detailed the principle of CSR across four domains (economic, legal, ethical, and discretionary), identified processes of corporate social responsiveness (including environmental assessment, stakeholder management, and issues management), and reorganized Wartick and Cochran's policies into a new category concerned with the outcomes of corporate behavior.

Wood's interpretation offered an expanded view of Carroll's four-part CSR definition, emphasizing the importance of a firm striving to be profitable, law-abiding, ethical, and a good corporate citizen.

In the 1980s, Thomas M. Jones contributed to the CSR dialogue by discussing corporate obligations. He argued that these obligations should be voluntary and broad, extending beyond traditional duties to shareholders to include other societal groups like customers, employees, suppliers, and neighboring communities. This perspective highlighted the expanding scope and complexity of CSR, reflecting a growing understanding of the diverse roles and responsibilities of corporations in society.

The development of the framework and hypothesis follows the review of pertinent literature and research. As shown in Figure 2.1, the model illustrates how two mediators—work satisfaction and organizational commitment—affect employee job attitude in relation to CSR.

The model's first starting point is the way employees see CSR. Distinct CSR characteristics may have an impact on workers' attitudes and behaviors at work.

Figure 2.1: Framework of the CSR-Behavior relationship

The impact of employees' perceptions of CSR on job attitudes and behaviors, as well as the relationships between employees' perceptions of CSR, job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and corresponding CSR Evolution 1999, corporate social responsibility, and employee engagement, were the sources of the CSR perceptions. This article's volumes are 125, 17, 28, and 154.

The only source of information used to measure employees' attitudes towards their jobs was an article titled "The Impact of Employees' Perception of Corporate Social Responsibility on Job Attitudes and Behaviours," which also discussed the relationships between employees' perceptions of CSR and their personalities, job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and performance, as well as attitudes towards counterproductive behaviour in business and CSR. The corresponding volumes of these articles are 125, 17, 100, and 13. The Impact of Employees' Perception of Corporate Social Responsibility on Job Attitudes and Behaviors" and Individual Behavior articles were the sole sources from which behaviours were measured; the respective volumes of these articles are 125 and 5.

H1: Employees' perception of CSR has a significant influence on job attitude.

H2: Employees' perception of CSR has a significant influence on job behavior.

Methodology

Quantitative research is a systematic approach to studying social processes by employing statistical, mathematical, or computational techniques to analyze numerical data. The goal of this research methodology is to develop and utilize mathematical models or hypotheses related to the phenomenon under study. Measurement plays a pivotal role in quantitative research, forming a bridge between empirical observations and the mathematical expression of quantitative relationships. Quantitative data encompasses any numerical information, such as statistics and percentages.

Descriptive research aims to outline the characteristics of a population or phenomenon without explaining the reasons behind these characteristics. It answers the "what" question, often using a categorical system or descriptive categories to define the situation or population. For the current topic, cross-sectional studies are appropriate and utilized within this time horizon. These studies involve observing an entire population or a representative sample at a specific point in time, differing from case-control studies, which focus on a smaller subset of the population with a particular characteristic. Cross-sectional studies are primarily descriptive and are neither longitudinal nor experimental.

In this context, a population refers to all the members of the same species or group living in a specified area, capable of interbreeding. Specifically, it pertains to a group of humans. Demography, as a social science, involves the statistical study of human populations.

Sampling involves selecting a subset of individuals from a larger population to estimate the overall population characteristics. The method chosen for sampling depends on the analysis type and may include techniques like simple random sampling, systematic sampling, and observational sampling. The selected sample should represent the general population accurately. In this study, non-probability sampling techniques, which do not rely on random selection, are employed. Data

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collection is conducted through closed-ended questionnaires.

A closed-ended question is designed to limit the choices available to respondents, requiring them to select their answer from a predefined list of options. These questions are typically formatted as multiple-choice or Likert scale questions. For this study, the survey was carried out beginning in November, with questionnaires being emailed to contacts in Lahore and Bahawalpur, who then assisted in distributing them to eligible survey participants. These questionnaires were subsequently mailed back to collect authentic responses.

In total, 204 questionnaires were disseminated during the survey. Participants rated their responses on a scale ranging from 1 to 5. The research design was structured to gather data on how employees' perceptions of corporate social responsibility influence their work attitudes and behaviors, particularly in Lahore and Bahawalpur. The questionnaire was divided into four sections. The first three sections were dedicated to measuring the five variables of the study using a Likert scale, where participants indicated their level of agreement or disagreement on a five-point scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

The final section of the questionnaire requested respondents to provide demographic information, including their gender, age, name, and the type of organization they were affiliated with. This comprehensive approach ensured a thorough understanding of the impact of corporate social responsibility perceptions in the specified regions.

The corporate social responsibility (CSR) of the employer was evaluated by the participants using a 9-item Sara Raouq Salman scale and Dan Zheng (2010). Things 1, 6, 7, and 9 are gathered from Sara Raouq Salman, while more things are gathered by Dan Zheng. The four dimensions of corporate social responsibility—economic, legal, ethical, and discretionary—are measured by these nine things. Section A of the survey looked at these items.

Job attitude were measured using Dan Zheng (2010) 8-item scale to assess Participant's job attitude. Job attitude measured the two categories. These categories are job satisfaction and organization commitment. Job satisfaction measures employee feeling about their job or organization. In this study it was self reported responses to likert scales. In order to get an overall attitude response toward CSR. Job satisfaction items were examined in the 1st half part B in the questionnaire. Organization commitment was measure with 8 items of the scale which was examined in the second half part of part B in the questionnaire. This portion is measured the emotional attachment to the organization, stay and leaving the organization.

This study used the instrument of behaviors developed by Dan Zheng (2010). Behaviors were measured using Dan Zheng (2010) 8-item scale to assess Participant's behavior. Items of behavior were examined in part C of the questionnaire. This questionnaire helps to find the behaviors of employee about organization.

Data Analysis

The data obtained is analyzed in this study to produce findings. For the analysis, SPSS version 16.0 was employed. The data analysis has resulted in the presentation of descriptive statistics. In order to determine the reliability and correlations of the variables, this study first analyses the demographic bar chart and cross bar. The data analysis portion also includes the regression analysis findings. The research model was put forth using theories and empirical observations. There is also a synopsis of all the theories.

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Position

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Manager	25	12.3	12.3	12.3
Non-Manager	179	87.7	87.7	100.0
Total	204	100.0	100.0	

Table1: Table of Position

Interpretation:

According to analysis in the position section, 12.3% respondents are manger. 87.7% respondents are non-manager. Graph are also presented the position of the manger and non- manger.

Experience

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Less than 1 yr	72	35.3	35.3	35.3
1-2yrs	67	32.8	32.8	68.1
2-5 yrs	35	17.2	17.2	85.3
5-10yrs	25	12.3	12.3	97.5
More than 10 yrs	5	2.5	2.5	100.0
Total	204	100.0	100.0	

Table 2: Table of Experience

Interpretation:

The information of experience is categorized into five limits which is less than 1 year, 1-2 years, 2-5 years, 5-10 years and more than 10 years respectively. In this study, mostly respondents are younger. Range of experience (35.3% and 32.8%) respondents are less than 1 year and 1-2years. 17.2% respondents are fall in the range of 2-5 years.12.3% respondents range is 5-10 years. Just 2.5% respondents are experienced more than 10 years.

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		Qualification			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Intermediate	15	7.4	7.4	7.4
	Bachelor	48	23.5	23.5	30.9
	Master	67	32.8	32.8	63.7
	Mbbs	58	28.4	28.4	92.2
	Mphil	16	7.8	7.8	100.0
	Total	204	100.0	100.0	

Table 3: Table of Qualification

Interpretation:

The information of qualification is categorized into five limits which are Intermediate, Bachelors, Masters, MBBS and M.phil respectively. According the survey, mostly 32.8% qualification respondents are master. MBBS job respondents range is 28.4%. 23.5% job respondents qualification is bachelor. Mphil and intermediate respondents range, are proximately closely near, is corresponding 7.8% and 7.4%.

		Age			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	20-25yrs	117	57.4	57.4	57.4
	26-30yrs	55	27.0	27.0	84.3
	31-35yrs	13	6.4	6.4	90.7
	36-40yrs	13	6.4	6.4	97.1
	above 40 yrs	6	2.9	2.9	100.0
	Total	204	100.0	100.0	

Table 4: Table of Age

Interpretation:

In this study chose the different age limits who tell the relationship of CSR with job attitude and behavior. The age limits are less than 20 year, 20-40 years, 41-50 years and above 50 respectively. According to data collection, sample size of age was above 40 but Mostly respondents were younger. The table and graph shows the frequency of 20-40 age group respondents are high as compared to the other age group which shows the 57 respondents are belong to in between the age of 20 to 25 and 26-30 years respondents' percentage was 27. 6.4% respondent's age were 31-35 and 36-40 years. Least respondents were older (above 40 years) range of respondent was 2.9% and

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only 2.9% respondents belong to age limit of above 40 which is less as compare to the other age group.

Gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Male	92	45.1	45.1	45.1
Female	112	54.9	54.9	100.0
Total	204	100.0	100.0	

Table 5: Table of Gender

Interpretation:

Data collected from 204 sample size. 54.9% the proportion rate of respondents are female who tell the job attitude and behavior about the organization. But 45.1 % were male respondent. In current scenario, compare male and female then the proportion rate of female probably higher than the male because most of female respondents were done the work well.

Reliability Test:

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.706	3

Table 6: Table of Reliability

According to Hopkins (2001), validity refers to how well a variable measures what it is intended to measure. According to Saunders et al. (2009) and Bryman and Bell (2003), dependability also refers to the degree to which data gathering methods and analysis processes will produce consistent results. Agresti (2009) states that a measure must be both valid and reliable, meaning it must properly reflect the notion being measured and describe what it is meant to test. It should also be consistent, meaning that a subject should provide the same answer if asked the same question twice. Reliability and internal consistency are terms used to describe how consistent a measure is. A scale's reliability is often evaluated using Cronbach's alpha (Cronbach, 1951), the reliability coefficient. According to O'Leary-Kelly and Vokurka (1998), a scale dependability of at least 0.70 is considered positive. "Acceptable" is defined as having a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.70 or above (George & Mallery 2003). The three components' Cronbach's alpha ranges about 0.706, indicating that they are all dependable.

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The independent variables' Cronbach's Alpha scores ranged from 0.591 to 0.592. The dependent variables' Cronbach's Alpha varied from 0.641, suggesting strong internal consistency.

As you can see from the Denzen article, the item's internal dependability does not match the required level, with a Cronbach's Alpha of less than 0.60.

Correlation Analysis:

Correlations

		Perception of CSR	Job Attitude	Job behavior
Perception of CSR	Pearson Correlation	1	.313**	.593**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	204	204	204
Job Attitude	Pearson Correlation	.313**	1	.473**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	204	204	204
Job behavior	Pearson Correlation	.593**	.473**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	204	204	204

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.16: Table of correlation Analysis

Interpretation:

When the coefficient of correlation (r) indicates the degree of association between two sets of ratio-scaled variables, correlation analysis is a technique used to quantify the relationship between the variables. R is a real number between -1 and +1. Little correlation exists between the variables, as shown by a value close to zero. A number that is close to 1 denotes a direct or favourable correlation between the variables. An inverse or negative correlation between the variables is indicated by a value close to -1.

The significance level of correlation estimates with two asterisks is $p < 0.01$, while those with one asterisk are $p < 0.05$ (2-tailed). On a 5-point Likert scale, participants indicated whether they agreed or disagreed with the statements concerning their attitudes towards CSR, feelings towards their jobs and organisations, and workplace behaviour. Previous research suggests that these factors might influence attitudes and behaviour at work (Schappe 1998, Peterson 2004, Valentine & Fleischman 2008). According to the outcome, correlation is significant at the 2-tailed 0.01 level. The variables have a stronger or complete positive connection when the correlation values are close to 1. Regarding the first hypothesis, the findings show that employees' attitudes towards their jobs are significantly influenced by their perceptions of CSR. Regarding the second hypothesis, the findings show that workers' perceptions of CSR has a significant influence on job behavior.

Table has been shown, H1 and H2 hypothesis are acceptable and strongly correlated.

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Regression Analysis:

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.594 ^a	.353	.347	.45087

a. Predictors: (Constant), Job behavior, Job Attitude

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	22.322	2	11.161	54.905	.000 ^a
	Residual	40.859	201	.203		
	Total	63.181	203			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Job behavior, Job Attitude

b. Dependent Variable: Perception of CSR

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.632	.308		2.054	.041
	Job Attitude	.052	.080	.042	.650	.516
	Job behavior	.763	.086	.573	8.908	.000

Interpretation:

The link between a dependent variable and one or more independent variables was investigated, documented, and evaluated using regression analysis. Employee perceptions of corporate social responsibility are the first independent variable, while job behavior and attitude are the first dependent factors. Therefore, we may investigate whether corporate social responsibility beliefs among workers significantly impact work attitude and behavior, as well as other interactions between factors. The dependent variable, which is as follows, is predicted using the following mathematical equation:

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2$$

Where

X₁ = Job Attitude

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X2= Job Behavior

where employee impression of CSR, denoted by Y, is the dependent variable. A is the value that Y is expected to have when all of the independent variables are equal to zero. X1, X2, and b1–b2 are the independent variables, or job attitude and behaviour. The coefficients or multipliers, b1, b2, describe the size of the effect the independent variables are having on the dependent variable, Y.

$$\text{CSR} = .632 + .052\text{J.A} + .763\text{J.B}$$

As can be seen from the above equation, the job behavior component has the largest value (76.3%), indicating that it has a bigger effect on employee perceptions of CSR than the other factors. Employee behavior inside the organization is generally successful; they work well with colleagues and provide guidance and assistance to the workers. The work attitude component has a 5.2% ratio, indicating that it has a less effect on employees' perceptions of CSR than the job behavior element. Additionally, the job attitude factor ratio is 5.2%, indicating a negative job attitude towards the organization. Employees' attitudes about their jobs and the organization are ineffective. They can leave the organization and gain the opportunity. This ratio shows that strategy is not well plan. Hypothesis I and II are support to this equation. The dependent variable is the adjusted R square, which is 0.347. The entire dependent variable is significant overall. The variance in the dependent variable that is predicted by the independent variables is displayed by the regression's R-square, which is 35.3%. 34.7% is the modified r-square. When the independent variable significantly affects the dependent variable, as per Baron and Kenny (1986).

Discussion

The conceptual framework may be verified by the SPSS model, which would also indicate if the framework is appropriate. The study's framework was verified by the programme. The SPSS model's outcome suggests that the conceptual framework may be used. The majority of the variable outcomes are in line with previous research. This research shows that employees' perceptions of CSR vary based on age, experience level, and qualification after analysing demographic data. CSR influences job behaviour to an extent that is at least equal to that of job attitude. This study commenced to assess the relationship between employees 'perceptions of corporate social responsibility and continuous improvement orientation and their effects upon employee attitudes and intended behaviors toward the organization. Job attitude and employees perception both are very important for CSR. But CSR mostly influence job attitude.

Findings and Limitations:

These can be possible limitation and findings about my research

Last but the least, there might be other factors that affect the dependent variable. This study took CSR perception and work attitude into consideration. Therefore some other mediator was not included in this study. However this study is an important step towards linking individuals CSR perception with work attitude and social actions.

I have applied my research on small and medium organizations and I have ignored the behavior of large organization employees, due to limited time and funding, participants in this research are obtained from

Convenience sampling. Therefore the results are potentially biased.

Summary:

CSR has been a hot topic in the management research field. In summary, the purpose of this study is to obtain a better understanding of how the employees perceive the CSR activities developed by their employer and what is their attitude towards these. The role of CSR in employees work outcomes has received growing attention. This study explored the effect of employees perceived CSR on job attitude (job satisfaction and organizational commitment) and behaviors. This study also looked at attitudinal constructs that exist between relationships of perceived CSR and employee behaviors. That is, relationships between employee perception of CSR and employee job attitude would be mediated by job behaviors.

This study found that employees CSR perception has effects on employees work outcomes. Employee play important role in their organizations and their perception of CSR will influence their subsequent work outcomes. The CSR programs would benefit both corporations and their employees. Organizations would also benefit from effectively interacting with their employees on CSR issues.

Employee perception of CSR and their reactions are different from other countries. More studies on CSR should give more attention to addressing the relationships between CSR and employees work outcomes.

According to the previous results and the summary of hypotheses, it is found that CSR has impact not only on customers, but also on employees. There are some discussions about the relationships and influence between dimensions.

Recommendations:

This study only focused on Lahore and Bahawalpur in the context of Pakistan. In order to generalize the result of the study to Lahore and Bahawalpur. Further research could extend the research background by collecting data from more areas of Pakistan. Gathering a larger and richer source of data will enhance the generality of results.

Besides, the future research could also address on how corporate social responsibility influence other employee or other measures of employee response to their work, such as turnover and productivity.

Finally, there are some suggestions for future research. The results suggest that the response to CSR and organizational commitment vary with qualification and age of the individuals.

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